

A STUDY ON ROLE OF EDUCATION IN WOMEN EMPOWERMENT

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Abstract:

If you educate a man you educate an individual, however, if you educate a woman you educate a whole family. Women empowered means mother India empowered".

Pandit Jawaharlal Nehru

Primary data is collected through administrating structured questionnaire from 100 women of Erode District. With the objectives to determine the role of education in women empowerment. The statistical tools used to analyse the study are simple percentage, Z test, Anova. Hypothesis is framed to find Demographic variables influence the women opinion on role of education in women empowerment. Thus the study concludes that demographic variables have a strong influence on education in women empowerment.

Key Words: Women, Education. Empowerment, Influence Variables, Entrepreneur, Family, Personal & Etc

Introduction:

Women empowerment helps to make people well educated so they are capable to take their own decisions in any field. The importance of women empowerment arose because of the sex discrimination and male domination in the Indian society. It increases the spiritual, political, social, educational, gender or occupation, economic strength of families and communities of women. In India women's empowerment heavily dependents on many different variables that include place of residence, age, educational qualification and monthly income. According to Pandit Jawaharlal Nehru "If you educate a man you educate an individual, however, if you educate a woman you educate a whole family. Women empowered means mother India empowered". According to Namtip Aksornkool "Women empowerment is a process in which women gain control over their own lives by knowing and claiming their rights at all levels of society at the international, local, and household levels. Self-empowerment means that women gain autonomy, are able to set their own agenda and are fully involved in the economic, political and social decision-making process."

Factors Influencing Women Empowerment:

- ✓ Existence of women's organizations
- ✓ Availability of support systems for women
- ✓ Availability of women-specific data and other relevant information
- ✓ Availability of funds
- ✓ Feminist leadership
- ✓ Networking
- ✓ Favorable media coverage
- ✓ Favorable policy climate

Different Types of Empowerment:

- ✓ Personal Empowerment
- ✓ Social Empowerment
- ✓ Economic Empowerment
- ✓ Educational Empowerment
- ✓ Psychological Empowerment
- ✓ Technical Empowerment
- ✓ Political Empowerment

Review of Literature:

Yadav Sudha B, Vadera Bhavin, Mangal Abha D, Patel Neha A and Shah Harsh D (2011) assessed the level of empowerment of women in Jamnagar district. In this study a cross sectional was designed in rural and urban areas of Jamnagar district. A well structured open-ended questionnaire was used to collect data from house-to-house survey. Chi-square was used to analyse the data. The study concludes that a part of the women had no say regarding the reproductive issues apart of the women had no participation in financial decisions. 21.47% of the women faced domestic violence in some form and education; employment had a high impact on status of women in relation to empowerment.

Dr. M. Shunmuga Sundaram, Dr. M. Sekar and A. Subburaj (2014), aimed to create the awareness among the women about different empowerment and identifying the impact of education in women

empowerment in Madurai district. A sample of 455 women respondents between 20-50 age group were selected for the study. The collected data were analysed using simple percentage and Cronbach alpha coefficients. The findings of the study shows that educational qualification play important role in women empowerment. The study also concludes that women's empowerment is to be carried out only through the medium of education and it is very important to all women.

P. M. Sirumalar Rajam and Dr. K. V. Soundararaja (2016) analyzed the problems faced by the women entrepreneurs in Kanyakumari district. A sample size of 600 women entrepreneurs (SHGs) were selected by using multi stage random sampling and they are collected using interview schedule method. The collected data were analysed using F-Statistics, Index score and constraint index. The study concludes that women's participation in economic development that will lighten their domestic work load and release them for other issues.

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To identify the different types of women empowerment.
- ✓ To determine the role of education in women empowerment with special reference to Erode District.

Research Methodology:

Erode District is the study area selected for this research. Primary data is collected through well-structured questionnaire. A sample of 100 women in Erode District have been selected by using convenient sampling method. The collected information were reviewed and consolidated into a master table. For the purpose of analysis the data were further processed by using statistical tools. The statistical tools are

- ✓ Simple Percentage
- ✓ Z Test
- ✓ ANOVA

Limitations of the Study:

- ✓ The study is restricted to the selected sample of Erode District and hence the result of the study cannot be generalized.
- ✓ The statistical methods used to analyze the data have their own limitation.
- ✓ All the limitations of primary data are applicable to this study.

Analysis and Interpretation:

Table 1: Demographic Profile

Factors	Number of Women (N=100)	Percentage
Place of Residence		
Rural	55	55
Urban	45	45
Age (Years)		
Up to 25	20	20
26 to 50	51	51
Above 50	29	29
Educational Qualification		
Up to School Level	38	38
Graduate	41	41
Post Graduate	21	21
Family Income		
Up to Rs.2,00,000	24	24
Rs.2,00,001 to Rs.8,00,000	42	42
Above Rs.8,00,000	34	34
Occupation		
Employed	63	63
Not employed	37	37
Type of Family		
Nuclear Family	46	46
Joint Family	54	54

The profile of the data collected from 100 women shows that, 55% are from rural area, 51% were in the age of 26 to 50 years, 41% of them were graduates and 42% of the women's family income is in between Rs.2,00,001 to Rs.8,00,000, 63 % of the women are employed and 54% of the women belong to joint family.

Table 2: Z test between Place of residence and Role of Education in Women Empowerment

	Place	N	Std. Deviation	Mean	Z	Sig.
Role of Education in Women Empowerment	Rural	55	4.64	21.92	0.237	0.071
	Urban	45	3.09	21.53		

Table 2, it is understood that the calculated value is greater than 5% level of significance and the null hypothesis is accepted. It is inferred that rural and urban area women depends on education in women empowerment.

ANOVA was used to compare the mean score of more than two groups of demographic variables like age, occupational status with Role of Education in Women Empowerment

Table 3: ANOVA between age and Role of Education in Women Empowerment

Factor	Age (Yrs)	N	Mean	S.D	Z	Sig
Role of Education in Women Empowerment	Up to 25	20	21.7857	4.04168	0.443	0.777
	26 to 50	51	21.5161	3.88905		
	Above 50	29	22.0870	3.62959		

From the Table 3, it is understood that the calculated values were greater than the 5% level of significance and the null hypothesis is accepted. It is inferred that, on an average, women of different age group have the same opinion on role of education in women empowerment

Table 4: ANOVA between occupation and Role of Education in Women Empowerment

Factor	Occupation	N	Mean	S.D	Z	Sig
Role of Education in Women Empowerment	Employed	63	23.83	3.97	0.448	0.814
	Not Employed	37	23.55	5.15		

From the Table 4, it is understood that the calculated values were greater than the 5% level of significance and the null hypothesis is accepted. It is inferred that, on an average, women of different occupation have the same opinion on role of education in women empowerment.

Conclusion:

Importance of education for women increases women self-confidence and help them to find better jobs and they can equal to men. Women make demands on government for health care, social security and other rights for women. Women also play important role in making a nation development and guide it towards economic progress. The education of women is the most important and powerful tool to change the Indian society. In India women constitute more than 50% of the population which they are the toppers in education. In our nation education has a transformative role in achieving more just, sustainable and equal communities. The study concludes that educational qualification plays important role in women empowerment for their growth, development, economic improvement.

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